

Supporting information to “Date of introduction and epidemiologic patterns of SARS-CoV-2 in Mogadishu, Somalia: estimates from transmission modelling of 2020 excess mortality data”

SI Table 1: parameter values used in the model.

Parameter	Description	Value
N	Total population size	2.2e6
Δt	Time step for simulations	0.25 day
d_E	Latent period in days	\sim gamma($\mu=3$, $k=4$)
d_P	Duration of pre-symptomatic infectiousness in days	\sim gamma($\mu=2.1$, $k=4$)
d_C	Duration of symptomatic infectiousness in days	\sim gamma($\mu=2.9$, $k=4$)
d_S	Duration of asymptomatic infectiousness in days	\sim gamma($\mu=5$, $k=4$)
y_i	Clinical fraction: probability of becoming a symptomatic case if infected for age group i	Age-dependent, from (22), SI Figure 7
u_i	Susceptibility to infection.	Age-dependent, from (22), SI Figure 7
R_0	Basic reproduction number (prior value)	3

Supplementary Figures

SI Figure 1. Burial rate per 10.000 person-days inferred from satellite imagery by interpolating between data points provided by satellite images (for details of methods see the accompanying paper (18)). The color shading represents estimates with low and high population denominators.

SI Figure 2. A. Burials by cemetery. Barakaat 1 cemetery was mostly filled up by January 2020 and replaced by its extension Barakaat 2. **B.** Dates for which satellite imagery was acquired.

SI Figure 3. ‘StringencyIndex’ from the Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker database. We divided the months of 2020 from March into four periods (separated by solid horizontal lines) and took the average of each. The fourth period is outside the time window of model fitting. The values are equal to the relative reduction in contacts (transmissibility) if the effectiveness of the NPIs (NPI_scale) was 1 (100%).

SI Figure 4. Weekly fatalities due to political violence in the Banadir region (from ACLED database) compared to the number of burials, going back to January 2019. The infrequency of satellite imagery analysed before 2020 does not enable identification of acute peaks in burials that would follow a mass casualty incident.

SI Figure 5. Clinical fraction and susceptibility by age group. Values from the literature (22) (green) were approximated by a piecewise linear function (red) made up of 3 sections (minimum, maximum and a line connecting them). The linearly approximated values were used as model parameters to minimise model complexity.

SI Figure 6. IFR estimates by age groups, using estimates from (24). Adjusted curves were calculated by taking the logit of the age-specific IFRs and adding the values 1, 2, 3.

SI Figure 7. Dynamic fits with all seed sizes and IFR estimates, fitting the period of 2 March to 24 August 2020. Labels show DIC values and median estimates for the date of introduction for the five different population-average IFR values that we tested.

SI Figure 8. Posterior distributions of the three fitting parameters (R_0 , introduction date, NPI effectiveness (npi_scale)) generated by MCMC fitting, showing correlations between the parameters.

SI Figure 9. Model fitting restricted to the period 23/February-13/April with four different seed sizes.

SI Figure 10. Model fitting of the period 23 February to 24 August 2020. Labels show DIC values and median estimates for the date of introduction by population-average IFR values.

SI Figure 11. Model fitting of the period from 2 March to 2 August with large seed sizes up to 5000

SI Figure 12. Epidemic size for different fits